

Distribution and habitat selection of the Asian Openbill (*Anastomus oscitans*) in Peninsular Malaysia

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Abstract: Asian Openbill (*Anastomus oscitans*) has been recorded in Peninsular Malaysia since 2008 and their distribution appears to be concentrated particularly in Penang, Perak, Melaka, and Johor. This bird plays a potentially important ecological role as a biological agent, particularly in paddy fields. However, its distribution and ecology in Peninsular Malaysia are poorly known. We compiled historical data on the occurrence of the stork in Peninsular Malaysia from published and unpublished reports, and determined its distribution pattern and habitat use. We also conducted field surveys to examine its current distribution, abundance, and macro- and microhabitat preference. Macrohabitat analyzed with ArcGIS indicated the stork occurred mainly in paddy fields along the west coast of Peninsular Malaysia. This can be explained by the abundance of the Golden Apple Snails (*Pomacea canaliculata*) on-site especially during higher flood levels. In respect to roosting, the birds selected trees containing numerous wide branches and an average height of seven meters. Due to their increasing and persistent sightings in Peninsular Malaysia, conservation priorities should also be channeled towards protecting their habitat and preventing illegal hunting. However, more studies needs to be carried out in monitoring their density and population.

Key words: Asian Openbill, biological control, Golden Apple Snails, paddy field, Peninsular Malaysia.

INTRODUCTION

The Asian Openbill (*Anastomus oscitans*) is a stork in the family Ciconiidae. It is characterized by a relatively small stature (68 - 81 cm), a greyish-white body, and a notable space between its mandible and maxilla (Robson 2002). It forages mainly in rice paddy, where it feeds on mollusks, small fish, and frogs (Robson 2002). Historically, the Asian Openbill was widespread across mainland Southeast Asia and the Indian subcontinent (Robson 2002). Although its population size has decreased in recent years, the stork is not thought to be especially threatened and is listed as a species of least concern (BirdLife International 2015). It currently breeds from India, Pakistan, and Nepal eastward throughout Indochina (BirdLife International 2015). In India, it is found among other places, in Rajasthan, Bharatpur Bird Sanctuary and Kulik Bird Sanctuary. West Bengal hosts a massive population of the stork during breeding season (Roy and Sah 2013). Breeding colonies of this species are also common in Wat Phai Lom (central Thailand), Tonle Sap Lake (Cambodia), and U Minh Thuong National Park (southern Vietnam). Although being resident in these locations, the Asian Openbill is now dispersing more widely in Southeast Asia, which may possibly explained by changes in climate and food availability (Roy and Sah 2013).

The Openbill is traditionally listed as vagrant in Peninsular Malaysia (MNS-Birds Conservation Council 2010), then updated to native in subsequent years (MNS-Bird Conservation Council 2015). Prior to 2008, the only record of this species in the Thai-Malaysian Peninsula was an individual sighted in 1936 that was probably dispersed from Krabi Province, Thailand (Wells 1999). In 2008, the stork was documented in Chuping in the State of Perlis, Malaysia (Lim et al. 2011). After this sighting there were no further records until 2013, when birdwatchers reported flocks temporarily inhabiting agricultural areas, especially rice fields, in Penang and several areas in the southern part of the peninsula, including Melaka, Johore, and Singapore (Tan and Murali 2013). In this study, we compiled data on Asian Openbill occurrence in Peninsular Malaysia so as to understand the species' distribution pattern in relation to its macro- and microhabitat selection.

Historical occurrence data are often used to estimate population sizes and documented distributional changes in species (Metzger et al. 2007, Jones and DeWitte 2012). Waterbird communities are commonly influenced by factors such as weather conditions, rainfall, habitat quality, and food availability (Studds et al. 2012), and they can use a variety of natural or artificial wetlands, (Kingford and Norman 2002). We need to know a range of habitat required by a stork. In principle, the species is considered to be an indicator of environmental health because it is selective in its habitat use (Nachuha 2009). Its occurrence in Peninsular Malaysia should thus reflect the environmental quality of the wetlands in which it feeds. The occurrence of the stork is also interesting in terms of its diet. It is known to feed on the Golden Apple Snails (*Pomacea canaliculata*), a major pest in paddy agriculture (Sin 2003), being biologically controlled by the stork and thus would benefit rice farming. Finally, the occurrence of the stork should not only depend upon food availability and quality but also upon other factors, such as competition and depredation. Thus, we examined other factors that could play a role in site selection.

The objectives of this study were to document the distribution of the Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia, to determine its habitat preference by means of macro- and microhabitat parameters, and to explain factors that influence the distribution of Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia.

METHODS

Study Area

Previous data on Asian Openbill occurrence in Peninsular Malaysia were gathered during interviews with officers and rangers from the Department of Wildlife and National Parks (DWNP) and local residents at survey sites. The information included history, distribution, abundance and current status. Survey sites were selected based on secondary data and reports from the wildlife officers of the department. This survey was conducted in February 2014 covering 32 sites, 14 districts, and seven states along the west coast of Peninsular Malaysia (Figure 1), namely Perlis, Kedah, Pulau Pinang, Perak, Selangor, Melaka and Johor.

Field Survey

Birds were surveyed over a seven-day period at each site by Kamaruddin, with several sites examined in a single day. The data collected were: a) site location, b) estimated number of openbill individuals, c) macrohabitat (habitat in 5 km radius around a central point), and d) microhabitat (habitat within 10 m and 100 m radius over the central point). Macro-habitat data was analyzed by using Geographical Information System (ArcGIS software). Micro-habitat parameters on the other hand are: a) tree species and height, types of water body, and food types (10 m radius) and b) type of land use and flood level (100 m radius). Prey types were identified by examining the food materials the birds consume at the beak, before swallowing with the aid of binocular. We also recorded previous information from local residents about the occurrence of the storks at each site.

Data Analysis

Macro habitats were determined by overlaying the land use data (land used preferred by Asian Openbill within five kilometer radius) with the coordinate of storks in particular sites. Land-use categories were determined using ArcGIS 10.2.2 software and a land-use map provided by the Department of Agriculture. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation was run to determine the relationship between the abundance of Asian Openbill with microhabitat parameters in the study sites.

RESULTS

Distributions and abundance of Asian Openbill in previous and current data

Table 1 lists the distribution and abundance of Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia based on previous and current data. Beseri site previously was their roosting site, but was not occupied during current survey, whereas Tasik Gelugor and Mukim 10 sites are currently roosting sites, but were not in previous data. Current survey indicated that the Beseri site has been converted into a construction area. Several individuals of Asian Openbill sighted at Tasik Gelugor could probably be from the same group from Air Hitam Educational Park because the distance between these two sites is around 1 to 2 km only.

Macrohabitat

Analysis of macrohabitat with GIS produced ten land use types selected by the Asian Openbill (Figure 2). Paddy field constitutes the highest area used by the stork for feeding, resting, and roosting activities with 1010.79 km², followed by oil palm plantation, town and housing, and other plantations. The rest of land use types were recorded with the value below 200 km² by which the bog is least selected. Figure 3 illustrated the distribution of sites in the current survey constituting within paddy area all around Peninsular Malaysia.

Microhabitat

In total, there were ten species of trees recorded across all the survey sites (Table 3). The most common species are *Mangifera* sp., *Albizia saman*, *Elaeis guineensis* and *Leucaena leucocephala*. The height of trees recorded ranging from 4-11 m with an average height of 7 m. The obvious features of the trees are wide canopy structure with many branches. The Golden Apple Snails (*Pomacea canaliculata*) is the most common species of prey consumed by the stork across all the study sites. Asian Openbill were frequently found at the paddy fields rather than oil palm field or recreational park.

Three categories of food preyed upon were recorded during the survey which were, 1) Golden Apple Snails, 2) small fish (e.g. Tilapia), and 3) combined Golden Apple Snails and small fish. Of the total percentage of prey species consumed, it was determined that Golden Apple Snails constituted 91%, small fish 6% and the combined diet of Golden Apple Snails and small fish, only 3%. Spearman's rank-order correlation showed a positive correlation between the abundance of Asian Openbill with prey categories but this correlation was not statistically significant ($n = 28$, $r_s = 0.259$, $P = 0.183$). Only paddy field was used in this analysis and which constituted 28 sites out of 32 sites. Spearman's rank-order correlation also showed a strong positive and significant correlation between the abundance of Asian Openbill at paddy field flood level ($n = 28$, $r_s = 0.884$, $P < 0.001$).

DISCUSSION

The distribution pattern of Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia is concentrated along the west coast regions, distributing along the northern to southern states of the Peninsula and there were no sightings reported of its inhabitation in the east coast region. In terms of landscapes, west coast regions composed more areas of wetland, shoreline, marshes, mangrove and agriculture (paddy) compared to the east coast region. This habitat availability sustains favourably for the foraging waterbirds and likewise is an important reason for the Asian Openbill are mostly found in the west coast regions. Further, results from the Annual Waterbird Census (AWC) from 1987 to 2007 also suggested the west coast is a significant flyway route of 106 waterbird species along Peninsular Malaysia (Li et al. 2007). There are two possible events that could be the reason for the migration of Asian Openbill from Thailand into Peninsular Malaysia in early 2013 which are due to i) habitat loss from serious drought condition in Thailand 26 provinces and, ii) over population of this bird species found in Thailand.

The Asian Openbill was predominantly sighted at the paddy fields rather than recreational park or other plantation areas. Many aquatic organisms, invertebrates and other prey species for waterbirds live abundantly in paddy fields in which various aquatic, semi-aquatic vegetation and patches of water regime with different depths can be found. Paddy fields are manmade wetlands that provides an alternative habitat to support all life stages of waterbirds (Connor and Gabor 2006). Almost 15 out of 28 sites of paddy field in the current survey undertaken failed to record any sightings of the Asian Openbill. Most of the paddy fields were dried out as the farmers had already harvested their yield. While the flooded areas visited during the survey, numerous sightings of Asian Openbill were spotted. This implies that the dry and flooded condition of paddy fields may influence the presence of Asian Openbill. Nachuha (2009) mentioned that the dispersion of waterbirds in paddy fields was not random, but corresponded to the paddy phase. Phase one is characterized by a soft muddy field and shallow water with short vegetation of rice plants, thus increase the accessibility of waterbirds to catch its prey especially snails and small aquatic organisms (Fredrickson and Reid 1986). Phase two and three are harvesting period. Generally, the abundance of snail during phase two and three are less than phase one. Waterbirds are most commonly sighted on ploughed field in phase one rather than phase two and phase three.

Asian Openbills were frequently observed perching on trees with height varying from 4-11 m. The obvious features of trees are wide with many branches. In India, it is frequently observed that the Asian Openbills sought shelter at the highest branches of a tree and they usually build their nest at 5-18 m height from the ground (Pramanik et al. 2009). These features are important to support the social behavior of Asian Openbill, as they usually perch in a colony rather than in small numbers. Interestingly during the survey, the bird was observed foraging within its own group without interfering with other waterbird species.

Golden Apple Snails is the most common prey species that was observed across all survey sites. It is a freshwater gastropod molluscs, native to the West Indies, Central America, and South America (Pain 1972). It is distributed in most of South East Asian countries including Thailand and Indonesia where people cultivated and traded this snail for a source of protein. Unfortunately, these snails subsequently escaped to invade most freshwater regions especially paddy field and became a major pest on rice plantations. As water is available, these snails can mate at any time of the day in any season of the year (Naylor 1996). It can be classified as a fast reproducing organism as female snails can lay eggs weekly in 50-500 eggs at a time, with an 80% hatchability rate (Joshi 2007). Interestingly, the main diet of the Asian Openbill in Thailand and India is Golden Apple Snails. Asian Openbill prefer to feed on the adult and large snails, thus the remaining small snails will grow up and replace the adult population. This kind of growth pattern has made this snail a sustainable food source for the Asian Openbill (Sawangproh et al. 2012).

Food and paddy flood level could be the factors to shape the distribution of Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia. Results from this study indicated a strong association between the abundance of Asian Openbill found in the paddy fields with the presence of its prey; particularly the snails. Another strong positive correlation of the Asian Openbill found in the flooded rice field is the preference of this stork in the flooded areas rather than dried ones, may be the abundance of the Golden Apple Snails found at the rice growing stage. This finding is also similar to Sawangproh et al. (2012)'s study in Thailand, where the abundance of Golden Apple Snails in most flooded paddy fields were positively correlated with the abundance of Asian Openbill and the population size of birds is huge when the snail is abundant. Low et al. (2013) mentioned that the ongoing drought condition in 26 provinces of Thailand could be the reason for the migration of Asian Openbill flocks in Peninsular Malaysia. Sharma (2007) stated that the large population of Asian Openbill in India especially at Raiganj Bird Sanctuary was influenced by the existence of many flood plains such as rice paddies, large water bodies, marsh areas, and riverine beds that were full of the snails.

Future monitoring and survey should further investigate the influence of Asian Openbill stork towards other waterbird species. DWNP should look into protecting this species under Wildlife Conservation Act 2010 [Act 716] since there is no evidence of any invasive threats to other local waterbirds nor other threatening issues reported on the Asian Openbill. Its potential role in contributing towards the productivity of paddy industry in Peninsular Malaysia must not be neglected. However, more extensive study needs to be carried out to understand the ecology, behaviour and interspecific interactions with other resident birds.

Acknowledgements : We like to thank the Department of Wildlife and National Parks (DWNP/PERHILITAN) for supporting this research under the grant STGL-009-2012 and their field rangers especially Mr. Hamzah Saad for his great support and generosity in providing us the information needed during the surveys at Perak, Penang, Perlis, and Kedah States. Special thanks to Mr. Fauzul Azim Zainal-Abidin for his assistance in landuse analysis. We also thank anonymous reviewers for the crucial comments and critics throughout the study period till this finding is successfully published.

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Figure 1. Study areas along the west coast of Peninsular Malaysia.

Table 1. Distributions and abundance of Asian Openbill in previous and current data.

State	Site	Previous Date	Abundance	CurrentDate	Abundance
Perlis	Kampung Behor Cicar	Jun-13	70	Feb-14	0
Perlis	Kampung Titi Tampang	Jun-13	300	Feb-14	0
Perlis	Beseri	Jun-13	50		No survey*
Kedah	near Jalan Langgar	May-13	80	Feb-14	50
Kedah	Pumpong Alor Setar	Feb-13	100	Feb-14	100
Kedah	Taman Ariff Jaya	May-13	80	Feb-14	50
Kedah	Kampung Gerigis	May-13	200	Feb-14	20
Pulau Pinang	Permatang Nibong	Jan-13	250	Feb-14	0
Pulau Pinang	Penanti	May-13	1500	Feb-14	0
Pulau Pinang	Penanti	Jan-13	300	Feb-14	0
Pulau Pinang	Permatang Pauh	May-13	1500	Feb-14	40
Pulau Pinang	Permatang Pauh	May-13	80	Feb-14	80
Pulau Pinang	Tasek Gelugor			Feb-14	20
Pulau Pinang	Air Hitam Educational Park	May-13	200	Feb-14	200
Pulau Pinang	Mukim 10		Newly	Feb-14	230
Pulau Pinang	Sungai Acheh	Jan-13	1300	Feb-14	0
Pulau Pinang	Pinang Tunggal	Apr-13	800	Feb-14	0
Pulau Pinang	Bumbung lima	Jul-13	3874	Feb-14	5
Perak	Pandak Putih	Sep-13	50	Feb-14	0
Perak	Bagan Tiang	Jan-13	2000	Feb-14	100
Perak	Simpang Lima	Jun-13	150	Feb-14	0
Perak	Parit Buntar	Jun-13	200	Feb-14	0
Perak	Sungai Bakau	Jan-13	400	Feb-14	0
Perak	Kampung Chui Chak	Dec-13	250	Feb-14	0
Perak	Sungai Manik	May-13	200	Feb-14	300
Perak	kampung gajah	Jan-13	200	Feb-14	0
Perak	Seberang Perak	Jul-13	100	Feb-14	0
Selangor	Tanjung Karang	Jul-13	150	Feb-14	0
Malacca	Bukit Rambai	Nov-12	300	Feb-14	250
Malacca	Bachang	Dec-13	150	Feb-14	0
Malacca	Bukit Lintang	Jan-13	300	Feb-14	50
Johore	Telok Rimba	Jan-13	350	Feb-14	0
Johore	Sawah Sg. Ring	Jan-13	30	Feb-14	0

Note: *no survey was carried out due to construction taking place during the survey.

Figure 2. Comparison between ten largest land use areas (km²) used by Asian Openbill in Peninsular Malaysia.

Figure 3. Distribution of the Asian Openbill at paddy fields in Peninsular Malaysia.

Table 2. Microhabitats at all study sites

Penang	Bumbang lima	<i>Antidesma</i> sp.	7	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	Pandak Putih	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	5	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	Bagan Tiang	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	7	small fish (e.g. <i>Tilapia</i> sp.)	pond	ricefield
Perak	Simpang Lima	<i>Albizia saman</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	Parit Buntar	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	10	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	oil palm
Perak	Sungai Bakau	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	Kampung Chui Chak	<i>Albizia saman</i>	8	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	Sungai Manik	<i>Mangifera indica</i> , <i>Elaeis guineensis</i> and <i>Antidesma</i> sp.	7	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perak	kampung gajah	<i>Albizia saman</i>	7	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ridefield
Perak	Seberang Perak	<i>Muntingia calabura</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ridefield
Selangor	Tanjung Karang	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	5	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Malacca	Bukit Rambai	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> and <i>Muntingia calabura</i>	7	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Malacca	Bachang	<i>Mangifera</i> sp. and <i>Muntingia calabura</i>	4	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Malacca	Bukit Lintang	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Johore	Telok Rimba	<i>Azadirachta excelsa</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	pond	ricefield
Johore	Sawah Sg. Ring	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	4	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ridefield

Table 2. Microhabitats at all study sites

State	Site	Tree Species	Tree Height (m)	Prey	Water Body	Landuse
Perlis	Kampung Behor Cicar	<i>Albizia saman</i>	5	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Perlis	Kampung Titi Tampang	<i>Albizia saman</i>	5	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Kedah	near Jalan Langgar	<i>Albizia saman</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Kedah	Pumpong Alor Setar	<i>Antidesma</i> sp.	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Kedah	Taman Ariff Jaya	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	pond	ricefield
Kedah	Kampung Gerigis	<i>Antidesma</i> sp.	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Pernatang Nibong	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	4.5	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Penanti	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	9	small fish (e.g. Tilapia sp.)	creek	oil palm
Penang	Penanti	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	10	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	oil palm
Penang	Pernatang Pauh	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	9	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Pernatang Pauh	<i>Azadirachta excelsa</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Tasek Gelugor	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	10	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Air Hitam Educational Park	<i>Nypa fruticans</i> and <i>Barringtonia</i> sp.	7	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i> and small fish	stream	recreational park
Penang	Mukim 10	<i>Albizia saman</i>	11	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	pond	ricefield
Penang	Sungai Acheh	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	6	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield
Penang	Pinang Tunggal	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	4	<i>Pomacea canaliculata</i>	irrigate	ricefield

Table 3. Tree species preferred for roosting by Asian Openbills

Tree species	Common Name/Local Name
<i>Albizia saman</i>	Rain Tree
<i>Antidesma sp.</i>	Gonciak Tree
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Lamtoro / <i>Petai belalang</i>
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mango Tree
<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Oil Palm
<i>Azadirachta excelsa</i>	Neem Tree
<i>Nypa fruticans</i>	Nipa Palm
<i>Barringtonia sp.</i>	Putat Tree
<i>Muntingia calabura</i>	Indian Cherry Tree
<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	Sea almond / <i>Ketapang</i> Tree

